

over the break-point are closed to those of the non-anodised metal. The value of ΔT at which the break-point takes place can be seen as a function of the thickness of the anodic film. The value of b below the break-point may be considered as a porosity-dependent factor, and greater the porosity the lower is the value of b .

During anodisation of Al, Al-Mn and Al-Mg in organic acids, the following competitive anodic reactions may take place: (i) anodic dissolution of the metal, (ii) oxygen evolution, (iii) oxidation of the metal to the oxide, (iv) Kolbe decarboxylation and coupling and (v) oxidation of the organic matter in solution. The Kolbe decarboxylation-coupling process was reported to proceed on Al during its anodisation in organic acids⁵. An evidence of this reaction is the formation of oily drops floated on the surface of the citric and tartaric acids during the anodisation of Al and its alloys under investigation. In the case of propionic, butyric and maleic acids, white fume was formed around the non-immersed part of the anode. The fume is probably the products of oxidation and decarboxylation of the organic acids⁶. Anodisation of Al, Al-Mn and Al-Mg in citric acid was accompanied with sparks arising between the anode and the acid solution. Anodisation of Al-Mn in tartaric acid showed the same phenomenon. The spark formation always left dark spots very similar to pittings. These spots may be the products of intensive oxidation of the organic acids.

The possible oxidation of the metal to the oxide during anodisation must lead to an increase in weight of the specimen. Anodisation of Al, Al-Mn and Al-Mg for 0.5 h in citric and tartaric acids at 1.0 A dm⁻² lead to the increase in the weight of each specimen by 0.0130–0.0156 g/20 cm². In other acids, the weight increased by (0.60–9.0) $\times 10^{-3}$ g/20 cm².

In addition to all the possible reactions mentioned above during the anodisation process, the complexation between the metals Al, Mn and Mg and the added acids is not ruled out.

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Polarographic and Cyclic Voltammetric Reduction of *o*-Nitrobenzaldehyde Isonicotinoylhydrazone

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ISONICOTINOYLHYDRAZIDE derivatives of carbonyl compounds are used extensively as therapeutic agents¹⁻³. *o*-Nitrobenzaldehyde isonicotinoylhydrazone is one such compound. The therapeutic action is generally related to the redox behaviour of the compound. Hence the polarographic and cyclic voltammetric studies of the compound in solutions of pH 2–9; and 4 and 8 respectively have been made here to understand this redox behaviour.

Experimental

o-Nitrobenzaldehyde isonicotinoylhydrazone (*o*-O₂N-BAINH) prepared by the reported⁴ method was purified by repeated crystallisation from hot aqueous alcohol and characterised by its spectral data, m.p. 236° (lit. 235–36°). All the other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

Current-voltage curves are recorded in Britton-Robinson buffer solutions (pH 2–9). A Elico CL-25 DC pen recording polarograph was used for recording current-voltage curves of hydrazone. The dropping mercury electrode had the following characteristics: $t=3.0$ s, $m=1.93$ mg s⁻¹ at a height of 85 cm of mercury column in water under open-circuit conditions. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded in Britton-Robinson buffers (pH 4 and 8) using cyclic voltammetric unit consisting of an X-Y recorder (Model RE 0074), PARC 175 universal programmer and PARC 174-A polarographic analyser. Metrohm 9323 hanging mercury drop electrode, platinum wire electrode and saturated calomel electrode were used as working electrode, counter electrode and reference electrode respectively. The results are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—HALF-WAVE POTENTIALS OF *o*-O₂N-BAINH AT DIFFERENT pH VALUES

Medium: 20% aqueous DMF, [<i>o</i> -O ₂ N-BAINH]=4 $\times 10^{-4}$ M			
pH	-E _{1/2} V vs SCE		
	First wave	Second wave	Third wave
2.0	0.18	0.63	0.84
3.0	0.21	0.75	0.90
4.0	0.26	0.81	0.96
5.0	0.31	0.90	1.06
6.0	0.36	0.98	1.14
7.0	0.42	1.08	1.24
8.0	0.48	1.17	1.29
9.0	0.56	1.24	—

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TABLE 2—PEAK POTENTIALS OF *o*-O₂N-BAINH AT pH 4 AND 8

Medium : 20% aqueous DMF, [*o*-O₂N-BAINH] = 4 × 10⁻⁴ M

Sweep rate V s ⁻¹	-E _{pcI} /V	-E _{pcII} /V	-E _{pcIII} /V	-E _{pcIV} /V
	pH 4.0			
0.050	0.92	0.88	1.00	1.23
0.100	0.93	0.89	1.02	1.25 1.33
	pH 8.0			
0.050	0.54	1.12	1.30	—
0.100	0.56	1.22	1.31	—

Results and Discussion

The compound exhibits three polarographic reduction waves in general except in solutions of pH 9. In cyclic voltammetry, four peaks in acid solutions and three peaks in alkaline solutions were marked.

The number of electrons involved in the polarographic reduction is established as four, two and four for the first, second and third waves respectively by the usual micro-coulometry.

Polarographic studies :

First wave : The wave appeared on the potential axis in the voltage range -0.18 to -0.56 V vs SCE and the half-wave potential increased linearly with the increase in pH as per equation, E_{1/2} = -0.02 - 0.059 pH. This suggests that protons are involved in the reduction process. The slope values of log i/(i_d - i) vs E_{dms} plot and the shift in E_{1/2} with concentration of the compound reveal that the wave is

irreversible. The limiting current varies linearly with the square-root of the height of mercury column suggesting that the wave is diffusion-controlled. A comparison of the half-wave potentials with those reported for the first wave of *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde isonicotinoylhydrazone⁶ or nitrobenzene⁶ suggests that the wave under discussion is due to the reduction of the nitro group to the hydroxylamine, since four electrons are involved in the reduction. This is also supported by the absence of such a wave in the polarographic behaviour of isonicotinoylhydrazide reported by Lund⁷. Therefore the first wave is attributed to the polarographic reduction of nitro group to hydroxylamine,

Second wave : The position of the wave on the potential axis between -0.63 and -1.24 V vs SCE, suggests that it corresponds to the reductive cleavage of =N-N- linkage in the hydrazone. Similar wave was reported for isonicotinoylhydrazide by Lund⁷. The effect of concentration of the compound and height of the mercury column on the limiting current suggest that the wave is diffusion-controlled. It is known that semicarbazones⁸ undergo reductive cleavage of =N-N- linkage to give the corresponding imine and urea. Hence the second wave is ascribed to reductive cleavage of =N-N-

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of *o*-NO₂-BAINH in solutions of : (a) pH 4.0 and (b) pH 8.0 ; sweep rate = 100 mV s⁻¹.

Third wave : The wave appeared on the potential axis in the voltage range -0.84 to -1.29 V vs SCE. Semi-logarithmic analysis of the wave reveals that the wave is irreversible. The limiting current varied linearly with concentration of the hydrazone and with square-root of the mercury column height indicating that the wave is diffusion-controlled. It is reported⁶ that imines ($R^1R^2C=NH$) undergo hydration to give the electro-inactive species [$R^1R^2C(OH)NH_2$]. Hence the third wave is attributed to the reduction of the amide (II) to the corresponding primary alcohol.

Cyclic voltammetric studies :

Cyclic voltammetric studies substantiate the polarographic studies (Fig. 1).

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Studies on Inorganic Ion-exchangers. Part-2. Preparation, Properties and Applications of Zirconium(IV) Selenite

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THE synthesis and ion-exchange properties of inorganic materials have been extensively studied¹. Although a large number of zirconium based ion-exchangers having different anionic part have been studied, no information is available about zirconium(IV) selenite. This paper reports the synthesis, characterisation and ion-exchange behaviour and the effect of γ -irradiation on zirconium(IV) selenite.

Experimental

Zirconium oxychloride and sodium selenite (Loba) were used. All other reagents used were of A.R. grade.

Synthesis : Zirconium(IV) selenite was prepared by mixing aqueous solutions of sodium selenite and zirconyl oxychloride in different concentration, pH and mixing ratios (Table 1). The dried product was converted into colourless H^+ -form by treatment with 1.0 M HNO_3 in the usual manner.

The exchanger (200 mg) was calcined at $850-900^\circ$ to get zirconium oxide (ZrO_2) and from it the weight of Zr was determined². Se was determined as free metal³. The mole ratio is given in Table 1. It was found to be stable in 1.0 M solutions of HCl, H_2SO_4 , HNO_3 , ethanol and 0.01 M NaOH.

TABLE 1—CONDITIONS OF SYNTHESIS AND ION-EXCHANGE CAPACITY OF ZIRCONIUM(IV) SELENITE

Sample no.	Mixing ratio	Concn. of reagents (M)		pH	Mole ratio	i.e.c. in meq/g for Na^+	i.e.c. for irradiated sample meq/g
		Zr ^{IV}	SeO ₃				
1	1:2	0.05	0.1	1.8	1:1.2	0.38	—
2	1:1	0.05	0.05	1.0	1:1.12	0.5	—
3	1:2	0.1	0.1	0.85	1:2	0.8	0.79
4	1:1	0.05	0.05	0.0	1:1	0.2	—

A glass-column (i.d. 1.1 cm) was used for column operation. The zirconium(IV) selenite (H^+ -form) (1 g) was taken in the column and the flow rate was initially maintained at 1 ml min^{-1} . A Global DPA-500 digital pH meter was used for pH measurements.

Ion-exchange capacity : The exchange capacity of the material (H^+ -form) was determined by standard method⁴. The strong acid capacities are expressed in terms of meq g^{-1} of the dry samples before and after γ -irradiations (a dose of 100 Mrad at a dose rate of 0.2 Mrad h^{-1}) (Table 1).

Heat treatment :

Sample no. 3 (Table 1) was heated for 6 h each at different temperatures in a thermostatically controlled hot air-oven maintained ($\pm 0.5^\circ$) at desired temperature. The ion-exchange capacity of the heat treated samples was then determined. The effect of temperature upon ion-exchange capacity is presented in Fig. 1. The effect of ionic radii on the exchange capacity is given in Table 2.

Distribution coefficient : The distribution coefficient (K_d) for metal ions taken in demineralised water was determined on Zr^{IV} selenite (sample no. 3)⁴. The cation-exchange loading for the system was less than 3% of the apparent ion-exchange capacity. The following equation was used for calculations,

$$K_d = \frac{I-F}{F} \frac{20}{0.1}$$